

Impact of Hydroxyurea Therapy on Clinical Outcomes in Children with Sickle Cell Anemia: A 5-year Study at Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi

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ABSTRACT

Sickle cell anaemia (SCA) is a chronic, debilitating condition prevalent in Nigeria. Hydroxyurea therapy has been shown to reduce the frequency and severity of disease complications. However, its uptake in Nigeria has been limited due to concerns about safety, accessibility, and awareness. This study aimed to evaluate the clinical and laboratory outcomes of children with SCA on hydroxyurea therapy at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria. A total of 43 children diagnosed with SCA were followed after initiation of hydroxyurea therapy. Data on socio-demographic characteristics, frequency of SCA-related events and laboratory parameters were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23. Paired t-tests were used to compare pre- and post-treatment outcomes, and adverse effects were recorded. The majority (65.1%) of the children were diagnosed with SCA by age two, and 60.5% started hydroxyurea within two years of diagnosis. Hydroxyurea therapy significantly reduced the frequency of vaso-occlusive crises (mean reduction from 7.70 to 1.91, $p = .000$), hospital admissions (mean reduction from 2.60 to 0.84, $p = .000$), and blood transfusions (mean reduction from 1.51 to 0.40, $p = .005$). Hospital stay duration also decreased significantly ($p = .001$). Laboratory findings showed significant reductions in WBC count ($p = .001$) and increases in MCV, while hemoglobin levels remained stable. Mild skin pigmentation and dizziness were observed as adverse effects. Low-dose hydroxyurea therapy in children with SCA resulted in substantial clinical benefits, including reduced disease complications and improved laboratory markers, with minimal adverse effects.

Keywords: Clinical outcomes, Hydroxyurea, Nigeria, Paediatric, Sickle cell anaemia, Vaso-occlusive crises.

INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a life-threatening monogenic condition affecting millions worldwide.¹ It is the most common inherited disorder in tropical Africa with Nigeria contributing about half of the estimated 300,000 newborns with SCD annually.² Nigeria's large population also accounts for approximately 100,000 infant deaths per year due to SCD, representing about 8% of the country's infant mortality rate.^{2,3} With a disease carrier rate of

about 25% and a 2-3% prevalence of sufferers, SCD remains a significant public health concern in Nigerian.³⁻⁶

SCD occurs when an individual inherits the variant sickle hemoglobin (HbS) from one parent and another abnormal hemoglobin (Hb) variant from the other parent. This second variant, may be another HbS or a different abnormal Hb such as Hb C, or Hb S- β thalassemia.^{6,7} When both parents pass on the Hb S gene, the child develops sickle cell anaemia

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(SCA), the most severe form of SCD.^{3,8} SCA is a chronic, multisystemic condition characterized by ongoing hemolytic anemia and recurrent acute vaso-occlusive events leading to substantial morbidity and progressive organ damage.⁹ Children with SCD frequently experience painful crisis, anaemia and heightened susceptibility to infections, with an estimated 50-90% dying before age five in Africa.¹⁰ In Nigeria, only 50% of children with SCD live past the age of 10, in stark contrast to the United Kingdom and the United States where over 94% of individuals with SCD survive into adulthood.^{11,12}

The high morbidity and mortality rates in Nigeria are largely attributed to delayed diagnosis and the lack of comprehensive care programs, which increases the risk of recurrent crises, infections and eventual organ failure.¹¹⁻¹³

Standard care for sickle cell anaemia includes prophylactic penicillin, pneumococcal vaccination, malaria prophylaxis and disease-modifying therapies such as hydroxyurea and long-term blood transfusions.^{2,7,14} However, in Nigeria like in other African countries, most patients do not have the benefit of an early diagnosis and even those diagnosed do not receive chemoprophylaxis with penicillin or non-curative but disease modifying treatments such as hydroxyurea.¹⁵ Despite been proven to be safe in children,¹⁶ and effective in reducing mortality,¹⁷ preserving organ function,¹⁶ reducing painful crisis,¹⁸ preventing stroke,¹⁹ and improving growth rates,^{16,20} Hydroxyurea use is still very low in Nigeria due to ignorance and concerns about safety.²¹⁻²³

Several studies have demonstrated the safety and efficacy of hydroxyurea in African children.²⁴⁻²⁶ While different regimens were used in various studies, both the high-dose,^{9,27} and low-dose hydroxyurea have shown significant benefits.^{28,29} Recent evidence suggests that low-dose hydroxyurea provides similar benefits to higher doses, offering an effective option for resource-limited settings like Nigeria.³⁰ This study prospectively followed children with SCA treated with a fixed low-dose of hydroxyurea (15mg/kg/day) to assess the pattern of use, safety and benefits among patients attending the Paediatric

sickle cell clinic at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital Makurdi.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This was a prospective observational study conducted between January 2018 and October 2023 at the Sickle Cell Clinic of the Benue State University Teaching Hospital Makurdi. The Hospital is a tertiary healthcare facility located in the state capital Makurdi, providing specialized care to patients across Benue State. The Paediatric Department, staffed by specialist doctors and trained nurses runs a dedicated sickle cell clinic every Wednesday catering for children with sickle cell anaemia from various parts of the state.

Study Population

The study included children with sickle cell anaemia attending the paediatric sickle cell clinic who were stable and receiving standard care, including penicillin prophylaxis, malaria prophylaxis, folic acid supplementation and hydroxyurea therapy. Children who were counselled and subsequently initiated on low-dose hydroxyurea (15mg/kg),³¹ (OYXUREA, Bond chemicals Ltd) were prospectively followed up through regular clinic visits. Only patients who had been on hydroxyurea for a minimum of two years were included in the final analysis.

Pre-treatment assessment

Before commencing hydroxyurea therapy, all patients underwent mandatory baseline investigations including: full blood count (FBC + differentials), Liver function tests (LFTs) and electrolytes, Urea and Creatinine (E/U/Cr).

Follow up protocol

Following the initiation of hydroxyurea therapy, patients were seen for follow-up visits at the following intervals:

- Two weeks post commencement
- Four weeks post commencement
- Every three months thereafter, once stabilized.

During follow-up visits, routine FBC and E/U/CR tests were performed and the results were documented for ongoing monitoring.

Data Collection

Data was collected using a structured, interviewer administered questionnaire. The questionnaire included provisions for biodata, age at diagnosis, Hb genotype, duration on hydroxyurea, and compliance levels. Clinical events related to sickle cell disease, based on national guideline definitions were documented before and during hydroxyurea therapy. These included: hospital admissions, vaso-occlusive crisis, blood transfusion, stroke, acute chest syndrome.² Hematological profiles including baseline values and 24-months post therapy values were collected to assess the benefits and safety of hydroxyurea therapy. Key parameters included hemoglobin (Hb), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), total white blood cell (WBC) count, absolute neutrophil count (ANC) and platelet counts (PLT).²⁴

Safety monitoring

To monitor for potential toxicity, other laboratory parameters such as alanine transferase (ALT) and creatinine levels were measured to assess hepatic and renal function respectively.¹⁶ Hematologic thresholds for toxicity were defined as:

- Hemoglobin level <4g/dl,
- Absolute neutrophil count < 1000 /cm³,
- Platelet count < 80,000.²⁴

Statistical analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were performed using IBM SPSS statistic software version 23. The student's t-test was used to compare the means of hematological and clinical parameters before and after hydroxyurea therapy. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH) Health Research Ethics Committee (BSUTH/CMAC/HREC/101/V.III/XX). Informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participants.

RESULTS

A total of 43 children were followed up in the sickle

cell clinic after the initiation of hydroxyurea therapy. Majority of the children (n=19, 44.2%) were aged 6-10 age years, while, 34.9% (n=15) were under 5 years of age, and 20.9% (n=9) were over 10 years. The male: female ratio was 1.5:1 as shown in Table 1.

Most children (n=28, 65.1%) were diagnosed with SCA within the first two years of life, while 14.0% (n=6) were diagnosed between ages 3 and 5 years and 7.0% (n=3), were diagnosed after the age of 8 years. Similarly, 60.5% (n=26) of the children commenced hydroxyurea within two years of their diagnosis, 16.3% (n=7) started treatment between 3 and 5 years, and 14.0% (n=6) initiated treatment after age 8. Notably, 14.0% of patients began treatment after the age of 8. The mean duration on Hydroxyurea was 3.02±1.01 years, with 44.2% (n=19) of the children on treatment for 3 years. Compliance with hydroxyurea therapy was high, with 90.7% (n=39) of patients adhering to the treatment regimen. There was a significant difference between the year at diagnosis and the year at commencement of treatment. $X^2=25.368$ ($df=9, p=0.003$) as shown in Table 2.

A significant reduction in vaso-occlusive crises (VOC) was observed, with the mean number of crises decreasing from 7.70 to 1.91 ($t=4.438, p=.000$). Similarly, hospital admissions, blood transfusions, and the duration of hospital stays significantly decreased after hydroxyurea therapy ($p<.005$). Acute chest syndrome (ACS) and stroke showed reductions, though these were not statistically significant as shown in Table 3.

Among the children, 90.7% (n=39) did not report any adverse reactions to hydroxyurea therapy, while 2.3% (n=1) experienced mild symptoms including dark fingernails and palpitations, as shown in Figure 1.

Laboratory findings showed significant improvements over the 24-month period of hydroxyurea therapy. WBC count significantly decreased from 16.63±12.4 to 10.61±5.63 ($t=3.619, p=.001$). However, hemoglobin levels did not show a significant change, remaining slightly below the normal range throughout the study. Platelet count

decreased significantly, while ALT levels showed a statistically significant reduction, reflecting improved liver function as shown Table 4.

The mean white blood cell (WBC) count showed a statistically significant decrease of 6.0233 ($t(42) = 3.619, p = .001$), indicating a reduction in the number of white blood cells over the treatment period. In contrast, the hemoglobin (Hb) level did not exhibit a significant change ($t(42) = 0.643, p = .523$), with a

mean difference of 0.9581. Similarly, the mean corpuscular volume (MCV) showed a non-significant decrease of -3.5860 ($t(42) = -1.192, p = .240$), indicating a slight reduction in the average volume of red blood cells. The platelet count, however, demonstrated a significant decrease of -62.0837 ($t(42) = -2.391, p = .021$). Other parameters, including absolute neutrophil count (ANC), creatinine, and alanine transaminase

Table 1. Social demographic characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency, N=43	Percent
Age group (years)	≤5	15	34.9
	6 - 10	19	44.2
	>10	9	20.9
Sex	female	17	39.5
	male	26	60.5
Weight	11 - 20	16	37.2
	21 - 30	21	48.8
	31 - 40	4	9.3
	>40	2	4.7

Table 2. Treatment details and HB genotype

Variable	Response	Frequency, N=43	Percent	Mean (yrs)	X ²	P-value
Age at diagnosis	≤2	28	65.1	3.02±2.86	25.368	0.003
	3-5	6	14.0			
	6-8	6	14.0			
	>8	3	7.0			
Age at commencement of treatment	≤2	26	60.5	3.37±3.17		
	3-5	7	16.3			
	6-8	4	9.3			
	>8	6	14.0			
Duration on hydroxyurea	2.00	11	25.6	3.02±1.01		
	3.00	19	44.2			
	4.00	6	14.0			
	5.00	7	16.3			
Level of Compliance	Not regular	4	9.3			
	Regular	39	90.7			
Hb genotype	HbSC	1	2.3			
	HbSS	42	97.7			

Table 3. Impact of hydroxyurea on sickle cell disease events.

SCA Events	Mean before Hydroxyurea	Mean after Hydroxyurea	T	Df	p-Value
VOC	7.70	1.91	4.438	42	.000
ACS	1.09	0.21	1.703	42	.096
Hospital admission	2.60	0.84	5.022	42	.000
Blood transfusion	1.51	0.40	2.951	42	.005
Duration of admission	6.26	2.09	3.544	42	.001
Dactylitis	1.81	0.23	2.304	42	.026
Stroke	0.12	0.00	1.703	42	.096
Splenomegaly	0.16	0.02	2.216	42	.032
Priapism	0.00	0.09	-1.000	42	.323
Malaria	2.84	1.07	2.907	42	.006
Gastroenteritis	0.56	0.21	1.886	42	.066
Sepsis	0.30	0.21	.662	42	.511
Osteomyelitis	0.07	0.02	1.000	42	.323
Death	0.00	0.00			

Table 4. Laboratory findings at baseline and during the course of using Hydroxyurea.

Parameter	Baseline	6 Months	12 Months	18 Months	24 Months
WBC (10 ³ /nL)	16.63±12.4	10.93±6.09	11.54±6.07	11.81±6.48	10.61±5.63
Hb (g/dL)	9.92±9.87	9.05±2.62	9.48±3.61	9.11±2.17	8.96±2.13
MCV (fL)	80.34±19.98	88.69±35.89	87.13±9.58	84.62±8.60	83.93±7.04
Platelet count (10 ³ /nL)	291.42±118.40	317.83±168.97	269.45±123.95	302.96±133.56	353.50±183.43
ANC (10 ³ /nL)	13.30±37.66	8.00±9.20	7.15±9.44	7.79±11.03	7.00±9.97
Creatinine (nM/L)	50.98±13.86	49.74±14.07	49.22±13.61	47.97±16.68	54.88±10.65
ALT (U/L)	34.00±19.02	52.89±89.35	23.45±12.87	24.42±11.89	20.85±9.43

Table 5. Paired sample T test between baseline and 24-months Laboratory parameter

Parameter	Difference of Mean	Std. deviation	t	df	p-value
WBC	6.0233	10.9130	3.619	42	.001
Hb(g/dl)	.9581	9.7653	.643	42	.523
M.CV	-3.5860	19.7284	-1.192	42	.240
platelet count	-62.0837	170.2820	-2.391	42	.021
ANC	6.3000	39.3934	1.049	42	.300
Creatine	-3.9070	18.0143	-1.422	42	.162
ALT	13.1547	21.1489	4.079	42	.000

Figure 1. Patterns of adverse reaction due to Hydroxyurea.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that 65.1% of the 43 children followed up in the clinic were diagnosed with SCA at or before the age of two, reflecting a higher rate of early diagnosis. Early diagnosis is crucial as it provides the opportunity for timely intervention which is known to improve outcomes.^{32,33} This is in contrast to previous studies, such as those by Akodu *et al.*,³⁴ and Ojewumi *et al.*,⁴ which reported a lesser percentage of early diagnosis. The findings suggest a positive shift towards early identification of SCA in Nigeria.

However, despite early diagnosis, there was a delay in starting hydroxyurea therapy. This lag is likely due to persisting concerns about hydroxyurea safety, as noted in previous studies by Ofakunrin *et al.*,²³ Adeyemo *et al.*,²² and Chide *et al.*,²¹ Encouragingly, most of the children were adherent to hydroxyurea with only 9.3% reporting irregular intake. This could be attributed to factors such as ignorance or financial constraints, consistent with previous findings by Chide *et al.*²¹

The predominant hemoglobin genotype among participants was HbSS, which aligns with other studies on SCD in Nigeria such as those by Nnodu *et al.*,³⁵ and Isa *et al.*³⁶ The use of hydroxyurea was associated with significant clinical improvements. There was a substantial reduction in the mean number of Vaso-occlusive crises, decreasing from 7.70 to 1.91, along with a significant reduction in hospital admissions and a shorter hospital stay. Blood transfusion requirements also diminished significantly following hydroxyurea initiation. These findings are consistent with the reports by Ofakunrin *et al.*,²⁴ Wang *et al.*,³⁷ Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ Hankins *et al.*,¹⁶ Zimmerman *et al.*²⁷ Additionally, a noticeable reduction in stroke episodes was observed, corroborating previous research highlighting hydroxyurea's role in stroke prevention as noted by Galadanci *et al.*,¹⁹ Tshilolo *et al.*²⁵ The adverse effects of hydroxyurea were minimal, with only a few instances of skin pigmentation and dizziness, reaffirming the drug's favorable safety profile as reported in earlier studies by Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ Opoka *et al.*,²⁶ Ofakunrin *et al.*²⁴

Laboratory findings over a 24-month period indicated significant reductions in white blood cell (WBC) count, a known effect of hydroxyurea in line with findings by Zimmerman *et al.*,²⁷ Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ Ofakunrin *et al.*,²⁴ and Kinney *et al.*³⁸ The Mean corpuscular volume (MCV) increased which is consistent with previous reports by Hankins *et al.*,¹⁶ Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ Kinney *et al.*,³⁸ Zimmerman *et al.*²⁷ Although there was a minimal change in hemoglobin levels over the 24 months, unlike the rise reported by Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ the platelet counts increased, which differed from other studies where a decrease was noted by Tshilolo *et al.*,²⁵ Opoka *et al.*,²⁶ and Ofakunrin *et al.*²⁴ The absolute neutrophil count (ANC) decreased slightly but remained within non-toxic levels corroborating Tshilolo *et al.* findings.²⁵ Overall, hydroxyurea provided clinical and laboratory benefits for children with SCD, even at low doses with no reported cases of toxicity.²⁶

CONCLUSION

Low-dose hydroxyurea therapy in children with sickle cell anaemia at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital produced significant clinical and laboratory improvements, with few adverse effects despite a delay in initiation after diagnosis. The treatment effectively reduced the frequency of VOC, hospital admissions, blood transfusions and hospital stay duration while demonstrating a favorable safety profile.

Recommendations

1. There is need for continuous education of healthcare providers and caregivers to address safety concerns about use of Hydroxyurea.
2. Early initiation of hydroxyurea therapy should be promoted as this could further improve outcomes for children with sickle cell anaemia.

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